
WOMEN ORDINATION: BREAKING BARRIERS OF RELIGIOUS AND SOCIAL INCLUSIVENESS

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Abstract

The issue of women ordination has remained a matter of debate among some Christian denominations, especially between the egalitarian and complementarian schools of thought. The objective of the paper is to discuss women ordination: breaking barriers of religious and social inclusiveness. Each presents their argument from Theology, Religion, Sociology, Psychology, Philosophy, and History. Complementarians are opposed to the idea of ordaining women based on male-headship principle. Egalitarians strongly establish and support women to be ordained. This article theologically, theoretically and historically reflects this debate. The theoretical framework for analysis relies on Sandra Bern's Gender Schema theory, and Albert Bandura's social learning theory. The methodological approach to the paper is the use of secondary data, which were analysed based on their content and documentary relevance to the subject matter. The position of the paper is that there is no valid biblical or historical evidence to show that women should be excluded from being empowered to proclaim the Gospel Ministry through ordination.

Keywords: Women ordination, Complementarianism, Egalitarianism, Prophetic ministry, Evangelistic ministry.

1 INTRODUCTION

The argument on women ordination among various religious groups especially among the Christian Churches has become one of the biggest topics. This debate is over the roles of women in ministry. The question that stands as a point of many denominational division is this: “Can a woman be ordained?” Without doubt, these divisions result in churches that ordain women and others that do not. Consequently, this debate leaves many unanswered questions in respect to the apostolic ministry of the “called believers” in light of the use of spiritual gifts. As observed by David (2022, p. 35), “Almost every issue related to the subject of ordination remains unsolved.”

To some opponents, “The new trend was created by the converging interests of feminism, liberalism, church leaders desire to enjoy tax law benefits to ministers, questionable church policy revisions, and Church Manual alterations” (Koranteng, 2005). This group does not appear to be consistent with the Biblical position of gender sensitiveness to the divine mandate of evangelizing the world, restoring the lost image of God through transgression, and making mankind ready for translation and glorification. They seem to maintain religious and social barriers that place a question mark to God’s intention for creating male and female to play a functionary role in service to God and humanity. The sole thrust of their argument against women ordination is on the basis of an administrative role and not on ministry. From a more critical point of view, it can be said that their position is more of ecclesiology than theology

Some others saw it “as largely symbolic, proof of the gap between the varying cultures in the faith in different parts of the world” (Michelle, 2015, p. 21). In other words, what this group is saying is that the determinant factor as to whether this ordination should be carried out is on the basis of cultural norm. The question this cultural argument has left unanswered is “And it shall come to pass afterward that I will pour out My Spirit on all flesh; your sons and your daughters shall prophesy, your old men shall dream dreams, your young men shall see visions. And also on My menservant and on My maidservants I will pour out My Spirit in those days” Joel 2:28, 29.

Yet there are others said that the practice “could be used to cause schism” Michelle (2015, p. 23). This schismatic argument is not consistent with the above eschatological declaration in Joel 2: 28-29. A conscious study of this predicted Pentecostal experience would show that its purpose is to form a spiritual unified force that could conquer the forces of evil that has immersed the world in wickedness. It should be noted that for believers to be a unified force for a successful ministry, the position of one renowned scholar show that the argument on schism does not arise. He observed that “The reality is that unity is not achieved by everyone thinking and doing the same thing around the world, but rather by getting along with one another while we do many markedly different things as needed in our varied cultures and the diverse world” (Patterson, 1985, p. 6).

In a hermeneutical study that was carried out by WAD (West Central African Division) Biblical Research Committee, having argued that previous discussions on the issue of women ordination was based on culture, policy, and theology, delved into finding answers to the question of male headship before and after the fall. The concern that this attempt in finding answer to the question of male headship has raised is that the concept of male headship applied to the church denies the Biblical truth of Christ as Head of His Church, Ephesians 5:23.

However, having highlighted various arguments on the subject of women ordination; this present study will take an approach from a meta-synthesis dimension to review the positions taken by previous researchers in order to arrive on a fair position. The objectives of this study are in two-fold. First, to discuss the significant role of women in the Church. Second, to discuss how their Spirit empowered grace is to be recognized, acknowledged, and accepted in the religious and social environment.

2 METHODS

This study is purely library-based research through content and documentary review and analysis of relevant empirical literature on the subject matter. It is not statistical in nature. The nature and sources of data collection were secondary through published and unpublished contents in textbooks, the Bible, Christian and religious magazines, bulletins, academic journals and synopses, internet-based materials etc.

3 CONCEPTUAL REVIEW

3.1 The Concept of Ordination

It is imperative as a matter of laying solid foundation to understanding the subject of argument, to look at what ordination is all about. According to Religion Britannica, “Ordination, in Christian churches, is a rite for the dedication and commissioning of ministers.” American Heritage has it to be “The ceremony of consecration to the ministry.” Another source rendered it that “Ordination is affirmation, blessing, and setting apart for a task of one who has been recognized by the discerning church as having the necessary gifts and formation for that task. The worshipping community, in the power of the Holy Spirit performs it, churchofchrist.org.

Etymologically, ordination is derived from a Latin word ‘ordinare’, means ‘to set in order’ or to organize’. The word was Latin language to ‘to appoint to office’ (Elwell, 2001 as cited in Okereke & Okoroafor, 2023). Traditionally, ordination confers power and authority on a person to act and be established in the hierarchy of orders. From the spiritual point of view, ordination means the outward calling of a person to ordained ministry resulting to the inward calling of the Holy Spirit. This assertion means that ordination is not just the ordinary work carried by human beings but a fulfillment of God’s divine plan in a person’s life (Yarkum, 2008 as cited in Okereke & Okoroafor, 2023).

3.2 The Concept of Complementarianism

As observed by Duncan (2004, p. 29), “The school of thought that is opposed to female ordination is generally referred to as complementarianism. This term denotes a classical viewpoint on gender issues. Generally, Complementarians hold the opinion that God has created men and women equal in their essential dignity and human personhood, but different and complementary in function with male headship in the home and in the Church. Daniel and Robert (2015) have argued that women and men are created equally, though, their function varies.

Consequently, (Koranteng-Pipim, 2005, p. 142) posits that “the Bible teaches that the male headship/leadership role and the female supportive/cooperative role were instituted at Creation.” The male headship in the narratives of Genesis 1-3, “some have seen this principle at work in Scriptural passages such as 1 Timothy 2:1-15 and 1 Corinthians 11:3-16; 14:34, 35” (Daniel & Robert, 2015).

To buttress this further from the Biblical references, Koranteng-Pipim (2005) posits that:

...when Paul writes that “the Head of every man is Christ, the head of a woman is her husband, and the Head of Christ is God” (1 Corinthians 11:3,

RSV), and that women should not “have authority over men” because “Adam was formed first” (1 Timothy 2:12-15, RSV), he is not concocting an arbitrary “proof text” to justify his alleged concession to Hellenistic or Jewish cultural prejudices against women. As an inspired writer, the apostle Paul fully understood the theological truth of the headship principle as a divine arrangement instituted before the Fall and which remains permanently valid for the Christian (p. 148).

3.3 The Concept of Egalitarianism

Egalitarianism is a philosophical perspective that emphasizes equality and equal treatment across gender, religion, economic status, and political beliefs (Kenton, 2024). The concept of egalitarianism states that people should get the same, or be treated the same, or be treated as equals in some respect. However, the term appears to contain two views. First, it is perceived as “a political doctrine that all people should be treated as equals and have the same political, economic, social, and civil rights” Second, it is rendered “as a social philosophy advocating the removal of economic inequalities among people or the decentralization of power” (American Heritage Dictionary, 2003). From the context of Christianity and on biblical teaching concerning egalitarianism looks at the fundamental equality of women and men of all racial and ethnic mixes, all economic classes, and all age groups, based on the teachings and examples of Jesus Christ and the overarching principles of Scripture (Stag & Stag, 1978).

Genesis 1:26-28 states thus:

26 Then God said: Let Us make man in Our image according to Our likeness; let them have dominion over the fish of the sea, over the birds of the air, and over the cattle, over all the earth, and over every creeping thing that creeps on the earth. 27 So God created man in His own image; in the image of God He created him; male and female He created them. 28 Then God blessed them, and God said to them, “Be fruitful and multiply; fill the earth and subdue it; have dominion over the fish of the sea, over the birds of the air, and over every living thing that moves on the earth.

Consequently, egalitarians have noted the absence of a division of a distinction or responsibility of rank in the exercise of the God-delegated dominion in verse 27. From their point of view, there appears to be a solid re-emphasis that since the male and female bears the image of God, “both are given the task of ruling or governing the earth without any reference to differentiation on the basis of gender” (Bilezikiah, 2006, p. 56).

3.4 The Concept of Prophetic Ministry

Hartley (2017, p. 1) defines prophetic ministry as “a ministry that hears from God and speaks for God.” What it means is that it requires hearing from God through all the means by which God chooses to speak and reveal Himself, always by the Holy Spirit and through seven primary means—the Bible, circumstances, spiritual gifts, family/friends, His inner voice, angels, visions and dreams. All the prophetic, revelatory and manifestation gifts are involved in prophetic ministry as recorded in 1 Corinthians 12:1-12. It is on this note that Maddox (2023) has explained that prophetic ministry is the art of hearing and communicating the voice of God to His people. The relevance of prophetic ministry in the church today cannot be overstated, as it remains a vital tool for spiritual growth, direction, and guidance. According to Francis (2006, p. 8), “the Prophetic Ministry is the outworking of God in a Holy Spirit-filled Christian’s life as a direct result of his or her ability to perceive and recognize the present-tense word or voice (the Greek word is “rhema”) of God personally to them, and which is demonstrated by a commitment to be obedient to that voice.”

4 THEORETICAL REVIEW

Two theories would be taken into consideration. There are Sandra Bern's Gender Schematheory (1981, 1986) and Albert Bandra's social learning theory as a way to evaluate the concepts so far addressed. This will also help for clarification the ideas that have informed the position taking by scholars on the debate on women ordination in Christian ministry.

4.1 Gender Schema Theory

This theory posits that people learn about male and female roles from the culture in which they live. It was first proposed by psychologist Bern (1981, 1986). According to the theory, human beings adjust their behavior to align with gender norms of their culture from the earliest stage of development. This theory, according to Kendra (2020), "was influenced by the cognitive revolution of the 1960s and 1970s." Bern (1981) proposed that the human cognitive development when combined with social influences has a great bearing on the patterns of thought which she called "schema", and this is what dictates "male" and "female" traits. It is believed that gender schema has an impact not only how people process information, but also on the attitude and beliefs that direct "gender appropriate" behavior.

Consequently, the grave effect of this idea is that a person who is raised and lives in a traditional culture might end up believing that the role of a woman is in the caring and raising of children, while a man's role is in the work and industry" and also, it dictates a person's value and potential in that culture(Kendra, 2020). And upon this, people form schema related to what men can do and women can and cannot do.

Applied to this study, the theory demonstrates that those operating on strait-laced cultural norm do not allow even enlightenment resulting from advanced study to influence their thinking and understanding concerning gender roles. For example, a woman who attempts to pursue a career based on the norm might be viewed in this traditional culture as unfair or disrespectful. The woman must continue living with the cultural view that her only role is in the caring and raising of children. This is grossly erroneous.

4.2 Social Learning Theory

This theory takes into consideration the importance of observing, modeling, and imitating the behaviors, attitudes, and emotional reactions of others. It was proposed by Albert Bandura in 1977. A critical study of this theory would show that man is created by God develop behavioral traits that should be a model to those around them. Also, man by nature is prone to imitate behavior they have observed for a time whether masculine or feminine. As noted, "Bandura believes that humans are information processors and think about the relationship between their behavior and its consequences. As such, people would love to "behave in a way which is believed will earn approval because they desire approval' (McLeod, 2016). Social learning theory therefore suggests that social behavior is learned by observing and imitating the behavior of others.

This theory, if applied to this study would demonstrate that cultivating a character that would serve as a model for imitation, which the imitators desire to earn approval is not gender based. Everyone created by God both male and female has a role responsibility for those around them to imitate for a positive reward.

Taking from a Scriptural point of view, Paul urged Timothy in 1Timothy 4: 12 to be an example that is a model to the believers in word, in conduct, in love, in spirit, in faith, and in purity. Jesus Christ recommended in Matthew 26: 13 that wherever the gospel is preached that the kindness and hospitality shown to by Mary be told as a memorial to her. With these

instances, it is crystal clear that in the Christian lifestyle which models the greatest gospel ever preached is without respect to gender. The emphasis here is that in God's community, believers are composed of male and female, there is no provision whatsoever for discrimination or differentiation on roles. This truth is clearly demonstrated in the prophetic ministry founded by God Himself both the Old Testament and New Testament.

5 DISCUSSIONS

So far, previous sections have considered mainly the two opposing views in the ongoing debate. Views on complementarianism and egalitarianism have been presented in this paper. In this section of the paper the opposing views will be looked into from three different dimensions that is, prophetic, evangelical, and historical. Finally, the paper will also look at the eschatological implication of the debate on women ordination.

5.1 Prophetic Ministry Overview

Without controversy, either sides of school of thoughts have shown that their arguments are based on the biblical passages presented in their support. One outstanding truth presented by both sides is that male and female are created in the image of God to play a functional, ministerial role. "Practically, this is true in the interaction between the genders in their daily encounters. There are certain aspects in which maleness exclusively reflects God and other aspects too femaleness uniquely reflects God" (Daniel & Robert, 2015, p. 52). This reflection of God by both genders is captured in the manner in which God, the Holy Spirit, distributes spiritual gifts to all Christians, not males alone. The Apostle Paul acknowledges in the distribution that, "one and the same Spirit works all these things, distributing to each one individually as He wills, 1Corinthians 10: 11." A close investigation would show that some were made "to be apostles, some prophets, some evangelists, and some pastors and teachers, Ephesians 4: 11."

The purpose of this giftedness is for a comprehensive "equipping of the saints for the work of ministry, for the edifying of the body of Christ, till we all come to the unity of the faith and of the knowledge of the Son of God, to a perfect man, to the measure of the stature of the fullness of Christ, Ephesians 4: 12-13." There key elements from the proceeding that should be noted for emphasis sake. The sole purpose of the gifts is for (1) equipping, (2) ministry, (3) edifying the body of Christ, (4) for unity, (5) for the knowledge of Christ, (6) measuring up with Christ's stature and complete nature. There is no indication of gender preference here.

However, in order to lay credence to the main subject of this section, mention would be made of some women that were outstanding in the prophetic ministry. Women such as Miriam (Micah 6:4), Deborah (Judges 4:4), Huldah (2Kings 22:14), Noadiah (Nehemiah 6:14), Isaiah's wife (Isaiah 8:3), Anna (Luke 2:36), and the four daughters of Philip (Acts 21:8-9) who were called and chosen by God to represent Him in sundry times and in divers occasions, is indicative of how the Holy Spirit distributes these gifts. Other male prophets include but not limited to Abraham (Genesis 20:4-9), Moses (Deuteronomy 18:15), Jeremiah (Jeremiah 1:5), Elijah (1Kings 18:22), Isaiah (Isaiah 6:8-9), John the Baptist (Luke 1:12-17), Judas and Silas (Acts 15:32), Agabus (Acts 21:10). God in his original plan for the prophetic ministry espoused it of gender preference, rather created an atmosphere of inclusiveness. The question that needs to be answered is, "Does the prophetic ministry require ordination?" Jeremiah 1:5 read, "Before I formed you in the womb, I knew you; before you were born, I sanctified you; I ordained you a prophet to the nations." Prophets are ordained of God for special ministry. Since prophets are ordained, and in the prophetic ministry, it is gender

inclusive, therefore, it may not be logically sound to argue the validity of women ordination for ministry.

Theologically, “if God’s choice of people to represent Him on earth is not based on gender, then as well as women can represent Him as well in any capacity the Lord of the Gospel Ministry pleases” (Daniel & Robert, 2015, p. 54). As rightly observed by Tkach (2006):

Prophecy, by its very nature, seems to involve authority, for it means to speak words inspired by God. Prophecies must be “weighed” (1Cor. 14:29), but this is not done to disagree with God, but to ascertain whether the words are from God. If they are from God, they should be heeded. Modern preaching does not have more authority than first-century prophecy, and it is inconsistent to argue that women may be inspired by God to speak in church about everything except the Word of God. In Corinth, Paul allowed women to speak with authority in church, which indicates that, the prohibition in 1 Tim. 2:12 should not be taken as a universal or permanent rule (p. 154).

This Gospel Ministry would be considered as evangelistic in nature, since it connotes proclaiming of Christ’s salvation to the world. This salvation is not on basis of birth, wealth or fame, but primarily to those who believe and accept Him in their heart.

5.2 Evangelistic Ministry Overview

While the Bible is the main source for teaching and practice, its understanding and interpretation on any given subject is according to interpreter’s history and tradition. The foregoing debate center on women involvement and their role in ministry, would take a further step to consider arguments that surrounds it. Having established the gender inclusive nature of the prophetic ministry, much difference if at all may not be found in the evangelistic ministry as well, since it is the same spirit that is in operation. All through history of the church women have “played very significant roles, yet the question of their status in the church and, in particular whether they should be ordained has caused much controversy” (Ronald & Groothius, 2005, p. 29). As observed, “these discussions are influenced by theological presuppositions, ecclesiastical traditions, biblical interpretation, human bias and plain ignorance of the realities in many churches” (Kunhiyop, 2012, p. 192).

Without any of contradiction, having noted earlier that spiritual gifts were given to believers for specific purposes which includes “equipping” and “ministry”, it is imperative to show how members were added to the church. In Acts 2:41, 47 we read, “Then those who gladly received his word were baptized; and that day about three thousand souls were added to them.... And the Lord added to the church daily those who were being saved.” Here the rite of baptism was a precondition for acceptance into God’s church. Patterson (1985, p. 7) strongly argued that “in baptism all Christians are ordained to the service of the gospel.”

However, the question of spiritual gift impartation requires further clarification. It is true that the recipients have been identified, which is believers. Also, these believers have been noted as to have gone through the rites of baptism as qualification for church membership where the spirit empowering grace for ministry was conferred. Who and who qualifies for baptismal rite? Acts 8:12 read, “But when they believed Philip as he preached the things concerning the kingdom of God and the name of Jesus Christ, both men and women were baptized.” This Scripture also demonstrates that the rite of baptism commands no gender differentiation. It can only require a simple believe in the correct theological, and unbiased interpretation and teaching of the gospel. This point was given credence to by Moltmann (2000), as he observed that:

From the very beginning the community of Christ baptized men and women alike and put them on equal footing through the one baptism. That is undisputed, and has never been called to question. By doing so it recognized without qualification the fellowship with Christ and the experience of the Spirit of both men and women (p. 285).

The debate in this section so far has shown that the evangelistic ministry of Christ is not only male based, but as many as have been called and equipped by the Holy Spirit. It would be pejorative to assume that only a select few are ordained where it is believed that all church members have gifts (charismata) for service (ministry). Kittel observed that the Greek word “euaggelistori” means “the one who proclaims the glad tidings.” Its meaning is not rendered to be “any male who proclaims the glad tidings”, which suggests that it could be male or female. According to Kunhiyop (2012), through baptism men and women are equally incorporated into the body of Christ (1Cor. 12:13). Practical evidence of this equality was provided by baptism, which throughout the church’s history has been given to both men and women (Acts 8:12; 16:15).

5.3 Historical Account of Women in Ministry

The long history of sexism led to the discriminatory custom in most traditions of allowing only men to be considered for ordination, as studies have shown. However, despite this retardation from a cultural ideology, the new tide of resistance has contributed to surmounting this unsanctioned development. This breakaway has revealed that, according to Kunhiyop (2012), over the centuries, women have held influential leadership positions in the church. They have gone out as missionaries to preach and win people to Christ. A striking point of argument was captured here, “If God chose to give Mary a position of honor within redemptive history, we should not dishonor women by assigning them roles that are subordinate to those of men” (Kunhiyop, 2012, p. 34).

Similarly, Nicole (1984) argues that:

It is clear that the Scripture provides for women a place of unusual dignity and significance. It never demeans the activities in which primarily women are engaged, such as their functions as wife, homebuilder, mother, educator of children. To engage in these notable activities according to Scripture is not to choose some second – best option, manifestly inferior to the pursuit of an independent career.....there is no scriptural reason to consider women as inferior, as too often has been done in human culture (p. 1180).

Historically, it has been proven that in the course of women engaging in the ministry of Christ “many have paid for their devotion with their lives. Among the first of these were Perpetua and Felicitas, who were martyred in AD 202” (Kunhiyop, 2012). In fact, the list of the great women in church history is too long to mention. For the purpose of showing the correctness of this view, few names would be mentioned here. These include:

- Monica shaped the life of her son, the great theologian Augustine of Hippo in North Africa.
- Katharina von Bora married Martin Luther and was described by him as “the first lady” of the Reformation.
- Argula von Stauffer (1492 – 1552) and Katherine Zell were significant reformers in their own right.

- Susannah Wesley, the mother of John and Charles Wesley, has been regarded as “the Mother of Methodism.”
- Mary Slessor (1848 – 1915), a Scottish missionary to Nigeria, worked in Calabar to eradicate the wicked practices of killing twins and cannibalism.
- Ellen G. White played a significant leadership role in the founding of the Seventh - day Adventist Movement.
- Agnes Gonxha Bojaxhiu, popularly known as Mother Teresa (1910 – 1997), a Catholic nun from Albania, founded the Missionaries of Charity in Calcutta, India, and became famous for her service to the poor in India (Kunhiyop, 2012).

Other historical evidences from additional study show that in 1964 Southern Baptist ordained Addie Davis. In that same year, the Presbyterian Church, US (South), followed Presbyterian Church (North), which had ordained women in 1955. By 1970 both the American Lutheran Church and the Lutheran Church in America had ordained their first women priests. Similar event that look like dramatic development happened on July 29, 1974, when eleven women were ordained by three bishops in the Episcopal Church. This was accounted as an act of profane insubordination, but it became significant in that it demonstrated that women had broken through the stained glass-ceiling in a church that, like Roman Catholicism, had claimed that women priesthood was both theologically and symbolically wrong and impossible.

After several years of debate the Episcopal Church agreed to the ordination of women in 1976, and the ordinations of those first priests were on January 1, 1977. The episcopacy was next, with the ordination of Methodist minister Marjorie Matthews as the first mainline Protestant bishop in 1980. Barbara Harris was ordained the first Anglican bishop in the world in 1989, when she became suffragan (assistant) bishop of the Episcopal Church, a scant dozen years after the first women in that denomination were ordained in the United States. Chinese Anglican deacon Li Tim-Oi was ordained a priest in Hong Kong in 1944 (Matthews, 1996).

Among Jewish women, the ordination question was altogether doubtful. They were barred from becoming rabbis for the same sexist reasons, most of which spilled over time. Because of the prohibition, most of the women joined seminaries and engaged in pastoral practice while minds turned about. The first woman rabbi ordained in the United States was Sally Priesand, by the Reform Movement in the 1972. There is a long list to this account, but for the purpose of interest retention, attention would be turned to the eschatological implication of subject in debate.

Eschatological Implication

Eschatology from the Greek *eschatos* means “last”, “farthest”. A branch of theology concerned with the final events in the history of the world or of humankind. Merriam Webster. While we believe that this world will come to an end, while Christian believers are given a mission mandate by Christ to warn the world and get them ready for the Parousia, the continuous debate on the issue of women has serious implication. If it is not properly checked, it may lead to a polarized state among believers. As rightly observed, “We have to be cautious. We have to listen to each other and treat each other as brothers and sisters who happen to have different perspectives” (Mueller, 2013).

From a biblical standpoint, one main purpose of equipping the church for ministry through spiritual gifts (charismata) is to bring “all to the unity of the faith and of the knowledge of the Son of God, to a perfect man, to the measure of the stature of the fullness of Christ” Ephesians 4:13. Here, cultural norms must be watched as a condition against total involvement of all (male and female) in the propagation of the end time gospel messages. Mueller (2013) posits that “culture may be opposed to God, the gospel, and biblical teaching.”

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This paper has attempted to analyze most part of the whole debate with respect to the involvement of women in the Gospel Ministry as ordained ministers. Recently, the debate has accrued so much intensity among some Christian denominations. This debate has resulted to biblical, theological, and traditional division namely, Egalitarians that advocate the ordination of women and complementarians that oppose it.

From the biblical point of view, Genesis 1-3 is basis for their positions. Complementarians added 1Corinthians 14:34; 11:3; 1Timothy 2:12; and Ephesians 4:23 to further their argument. Complementarians are advocating that male-headship is a foundational principle that should extend to be a continuous practice of all people for all time. In other words, ordination is all about headship. Egalitarians however, allude to Galatians 3:28 in addition to Genesis 1-3 to support their stance that God’s original intended ideal is that a principle of maturity must characterize the male-female relationship. However, this paper holds as a view without any contradictions that there should be no hierarchical differentiation in the male-female relationship, mutuality should characterize this experience.

Having consciously explored most part of the whole debate from both sides, the article concludes that there is no concrete biblical, theological and traditional support to exclude women from being given recognition to their charismatic empowerment for ministry. Both male and female belongs to the corridor of true Imago Dei in function and status in order to fulfill the church mission mandate.

In line with the support of the paper for egalitarianism, it is therefore recommended that women should be ordained as ministers of the gospel of Jesus Christ in order to contribute to the spiritual need of the Church since women have made valuable impacts to the material wellbeing of the Church in all denominations.

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